

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

CUSTOMIZATION OF THE SYSTEM OF FORMATION OF NETWORK COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE, DIGITAL ETIQUETTE OF THE TEACHER AND STUDENT IN THE "ON-LINE COMMUNITY": ACTUAL PROBLEMS, EXPERIENCE, SOLUTIONS

Tapalova O.,

Doctor of Psychology

*Associate Professor of the Department of General and Applied Psychology
Abai University, Kazakhstan, Almaty, Dostyk 13*

Sheymardanov S.,

Doctor of Education (PhD)

*Associate professor, Deputy Director Institute of Psychology and Education
Kazan Federal University, Russian Federation, Kazan, Kremlyovskaya street, 18*

Galimov A.,

Doctor of Education

*Associate professor, Deputy Director Institute of Psychology and Education
Kazan Federal University, Russian Federation, Kazan, Kremlyovskaya street, 18*

Abdigapbarova U.,

Doctor of Education

*Professor, Director of Science Department Abai University
Abai University, Kazakhstan, Almaty, Dostyk 13, Almaty, Kazakhstan,*

Zhiyenbayeva N.

Doctor of Psychology

*Professor of the Department of Special Education
Abai University, Kazakhstan, Almaty, Dostyk 13*

Abstract

The chapter will present the results of the study of customization of the system of formation of network communicative culture of the subjects of the educational process. As well as digital etiquette as a tool to optimize the integration of participants in the "on-line community". The aim of the study is to determine the scientific and methodological foundations for the formation of network communicative culture and digital etiquette of teachers and students in the digital space of the "on-line community" of the university. Virtual behavioral interactions of teachers and students regarding network communicative culture and digital etiquette in online communities will be monitored.

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Keywords: customization, online community, digital etiquette, teachers, and students.

Introduction.

Exploration of novel realms of interaction and scholarly collaboration among stakeholders of university educational processes within digital domains entails the customization of systems aimed at fostering a network communicative culture (NCC) and the advancement of digital etiquette (DE) as a mechanism for enhancing participant integration within the online community. These dimensions necessitate meticulous examination and critical analysis of prevailing approaches and instruments utilized in the professional preparation of future specialists. Within this context, the role of higher education as a primary catalyst for societal intellectual and innovative potential development assumes a notably intricate and expanded significance. The substantiation of digital transformation in universities and the customization of education is endorsed in governmental regulations, delineated as a pivotal targeted strategy for a university's academic prowess, encompassing tailored training of professional personnel to meet labor market demands. The

customization of systems for fostering the network communication culture (NCC) of educational process stakeholders within the online community serves as a foundational strategy, constituting a pivotal and integral element contributing positively to the modernization of Kazakhstani higher education.

Our research endeavors to ascertain the scientific and methodological underpinnings for the cultivation of network communication culture and digital etiquette among educators and students within the digital domain of the online community. Network communication culture encompasses shared values, norms, behaviors, and practices that characterize interactions and communication among faculty and students across digital networks. This encompasses various online platforms and channels, such as social media, messaging applications, email, and forums, among others. Key facets of network communication culture include operational communication, wherein digital networks facilitate real-time communication, fostering expectations of prompt responses and instantaneous feedback. Networking

transcends geographical constraints, facilitating easy connections and communications among individuals from diverse geographical locations. Cultural diversity assumes significance as individuals from varied backgrounds engage in online interactions. Platforms like Twitter, enabling facile sharing of thoughts and opinions, foster the exchange of ideas, information, and media. Online or digital etiquette for educators and students delineates appropriate online behavior, encompassing rules of respect, courtesy, and decorum. Proficiency in understanding online communication culture is imperative for effective online interactions and navigating the dynamic terrain of digital exchanges [1, 2, 3].

Scientific and Methodological Foundations for Customizing the Formation of Network Communication Culture (NCC).

Tailoring the development of a network communication culture stands as a pivotal pursuit amidst contemporary technological and socio-cultural transformations. In the current landscape saturated with abundant information, it is imperative to equip future professionals with adeptness in effectively discerning information, differentiating between facts and opinions, and discerning credible sources from fallacious ones. The customization of Quality Communication Systems (QCS) is crafted to facilitate users in establishing an information milieu conducive to accessing high-caliber information. Furthermore, with the burgeoning exchange of personal data online, there emerges an escalated need to safeguard against its compromise and misuse. Consequently, customization of communication systems necessitates adherence to privacy principles, ensuring the sanctity of user data. In the digital milieu, susceptibility to manipulation and misinformation looms large; hence, communication systems must foster critical thinking skills, enabling users to analytically scrutinize information and discern the veracity of sources.

The World Wide Web serves as a nexus for individuals of diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds; thus, customization of communication systems should account for ethno-cultural idiosyncrasies, promoting multilingualism and cultural alignment of content. Within the realm of online interaction, ethical considerations are paramount, entailing the assurance of users' emotional safety and the mitigation of harmful behavior, encompassing hate speech, cyberbullying, and discrimination. A socio-psychological scrutiny of the network communicative culture among educators and students entails an exploration of interactional modalities, communicative dynamics, and relational dynamics within the online educational milieu. Of particular significance within socio-psychological analyses of SCM, as delineated by researchers and our perspective, lies the examination of diverse communication styles adopted by educators in their interactions with students within online settings. These styles encompass formal exchanges within class forums, informal dialogues in chat groups, and communication via messages and video calls, wherein the degree of social presence in

online interactions is gauged through emotive expressions, even when conveyed through textual means or emoticons [4, 5, 6].

The scientific and methodological tenets guiding the formation of network communication culture are anchored in insights gleaned from a plethora of scholarly disciplines: sociology, pedagogy, psychology, information technology, neuroscience, among others. The first approach encapsulates the sociocultural principle, elucidating the cultivation of network communication culture within diverse socio-cultural milieus, scrutinizing prevailing values and norms therein. The second approach, grounded in the communicative principle, delves into communication theories underpinning interpersonal and mass communications. The third tenet operates within the domain of digital technologies, emphasizing the requisite knowledge, skills, and proficiencies in utilizing digital technologies across social networks and internet platforms. The psychological perspective constitutes the fourth approach, spotlighting the organizational aspects of online communication culture, encompassing the study of digital behavior, virtual anonymity, self-regulation online, formation of online identities, and other psychological determinants. The multimedia principle, as the fifth approach, leverages multimedia formats and diverse media texts comprising text, images, audio, and video, elucidating their impact on audience reception and the formation of network communication culture. Lastly, the ethical principle, constituting the sixth approach, delves into ethical considerations and norms governing internet conduct, thereby fostering the formation of a network communication culture. Ethical imperatives encompass data privacy, cyberbullying, digital literacy, digital etiquette, and other issues germane to the ethical utilization of the internet. The development of digital etiquette among educators and students within the university online community is underpinned by scientific and methodological frameworks, including: 1) Ethical considerations of the information society, encompassing adherence to ethical precepts in digital realms, concerns regarding privacy, data security, copyright compliance, and responsible conduct in online environments; 2) Social pedagogy aids in comprehending the social and pedagogical dimensions of interaction within online communities, fostering the cultivation of communication proficiencies, interpersonal relationships, and constructive collaboration; 3) Examination of digital communication modalities such as email, video conferencing, chats, and social networks, alongside their impact on learning and interaction, facilitates the formulation of efficacious strategies for utilizing and managing digital communications within the university milieu; 4) Psychological investigations into online interaction delve into the psychological facets of engagement in digital spaces, encompassing trust dynamics, empathy, interpersonal communication, and conflict resolution; 5) Teaching methodologies involve the development of strategies and techniques aimed at nurturing students' digital communication competencies, as well as fostering comprehension of digital ethics and social norms in online milieus; 6) Educational ethics principles extend to the realm of online education, emphasizing cultural

diversity appreciation, inclusivity, integrity, and equity in assessment and interaction.

The cultivation of digital etiquette among educators and students within the university online community necessitates consideration of diverse scientific and methodological aspects, alongside an understanding of the nuances of online communication and interaction. These principles and approaches are applied in fostering a network communication culture, contributing to the development of a methodology for its cultivation. These frameworks facilitate the identification of effective strategies and approaches for nurturing a network communication culture. Interconnectedly, these scientific and methodological foundations delineate approaches to fostering a network communication culture in contemporary information societies [7].

Furthermore, the degree of advancement in customizing systems for cultivating a network communication culture is contingent upon the research conducted by scholars primarily affiliated with universities, research institutes, and technology firms, encompassing aspects of network communication culture system customization [8].

D. Boyd, a prominent figure in the domain of digital and media technologies, explores the role of online communities in adolescent social dynamics and the impact of social networks on youth identity. Boyd's scholarly endeavors encompass investigations into the societal ramifications of social media, privacy concerns, cultural disparities, and online identity formation. In her seminal work "It's Complicated: The Social Lives of Networked Teens," Boyd scrutinizes adolescent communication patterns on platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, questioning the influence of social networks on the well-being of adolescents. Through empirical research and insightful analysis, Boyd challenges prevalent misconceptions about teen social media usage, focusing on concepts of identity, privacy, safety, threats, and cyberbullying. She contends that societal tendencies toward paternalism and control hinder adolescents' development as informed and autonomous citizens. Drawing upon over a decade of experience and extensive empirical data derived from surveys and interviews with American teenagers, Boyd asserts that the challenges of reconciling with digital life lack straightforward solutions, underscoring the complexities inherent in navigating the digital landscape [9].

Elizabeth Dubois and her collaborators [10] conducted an exploration into the nexus of technology and policy, particularly focusing on challenges associated with algorithmic customization and content filtering on the internet. Dubois's scholarly pursuits intersect the realms of technology and policymaking, with a specific emphasis on examining the ramifications of internet usage on political communication and politics.

Ezra Zuckerman Sivan and Reagans R. [11] actively investigate the social dimensions of network technologies, including the intricacies surrounding the formation of online culture and collective behavior. Their work posits an optimistic outlook, predicated on the notion that teams characterized by high network

heterogeneity, wherein relationships traverse significant demographic boundaries, exhibit augmented learning capacities. Through an analysis of social network data, organizational tenure, and productivity metrics from 224 corporate R&D teams, the authors underscore the role of network variables in explaining team productivity. These findings advocate for a reevaluation of the diversity-performance discourse in terms of network processes that more directly influence desired outcomes.

Zeynep Tufekci [12] is renowned for her research examining the societal and political implications of social media usage, including issues surrounding algorithmic customization and information filtering. Tufekci meticulously investigates methodological and conceptual challenges inherent in analyzing big data from social media platforms, paying particular attention to the validity and representativeness of such analyses. Persistent challenges highlighted by Tufekci include platform bias, sampling bias resulting from hashtag selection, and the sociocultural complexity of user behavior aimed at evading algorithmic detection. Furthermore, Tufekci warns against the indiscriminate application of network methodologies from disparate domains to study human social activity, cautioning that such approaches may not always be appropriate.

The exploration of digital ethics and network communication culture within educational contexts is expounded upon by the following scholars:

Howard Rheingold [13], a distinguished American writer and public intellectual, has extensively investigated the impact of digital culture on education, particularly focusing on concepts of digital literacy and ethics. Rheingold's seminal works, including "Virtual Community: Homesteading on the Electronic Frontier" and "Smart Mobs: The Next Social Revolution," delve into the interactive dynamics and cultural nuances of online communities, encompassing ethical and social considerations, and the examination of cultural, social, and political influences on contemporary media spheres such as the internet, mobile communications, and virtual communities. Notably, Rheingold predicted and elucidated the phenomenon of smart mobs, elucidating their emergence as a form of self-organizing social structure facilitated by advanced technologies.

Sherry Turkle [14], a prominent American psychologist and sociologist, specializes in investigating the impacts of technology on human interactions. Turkle's research portfolio encompasses digital literacy, online privacy, online culture, and the analysis of digital technology utilization in education and its implications for social skills and ethics. In her book "Reclaiming Conversation: The Power of Talk in a Digital Age," Professor Turkle compellingly examines how internet communication influences social skills, inviting readers to contemplate strategies for navigating and advancing in the digital era.

Neil Selwyn [15] is a distinguished British academic renowned for his extensive inquiry into the multifaceted impact of digital technologies on the landscape of education. With a keen focus on the intersection of technology and pedagogy, Selwyn meticulously examines the utilization of network communications

for educational purposes, while also delving into the intricate relationship between technology, ethics, and culture within educational contexts. His scholarly endeavors underscore the pervasive presence of digital technologies in the lives of university students, advocating for a comprehensive exploration of various digital tools to enrich and optimize the learning experiences of students. Selwyn's scholarship offers a distinctive perspective by foregrounding students' lived experiences with digital technologies during their academic pursuits, shedding light on aspects that students themselves deem beneficial or hindering. Through an extensive survey involving 1,658 undergraduate students, Selwyn's research elucidates 11 distinct digital "benefits," spanning from the flexible management of study tasks to enhanced content review capabilities and facilitation of visual learning modalities. These empirical findings not only underscore the pivotal role of digital technologies in shaping student learning experiences but also challenge prevailing notions regarding their transformative potential in reshaping conventional paradigms of university teaching and learning. Selwyn's scholarly contributions thus serve as a catalyst for educators to adopt a more nuanced understanding of the complexities surrounding students' engagement with digital tools and technologies, urging them to critically evaluate the realities in which students navigate digital learning environments.

Henry Jenkins [16], a prominent figure in American academia specializing in communication studies, has made substantial contributions to the scholarly discourse on the intricate interplay between culture, education, and new media technologies. Jenkins's scholarship delves into the evolving landscape of digital technology and its profound impact on educational practices and online culture. Through meticulous examination and analysis, Jenkins sheds light on the dynamic relationship between digital technology, education, and online culture, providing invaluable insights into the ethical dimensions of digital interactions within educational settings. His seminal work serves as a cornerstone for the development of pedagogical strategies tailored to the digital age, offering educators a comprehensive framework for navigating the complexities of digital communication and ethical engagement in educational environments.

Susan C. Herring and her collaborative research team [17] undertake a rigorous investigation into the intricacies of online communication and digital ethics, with a specific focus on the behavioral dynamics and interaction patterns within online communities, including those involving educators and learners. Their systematic exploration provides valuable insights into the emergence and evolution of weblogs as a prevalent form of internet communication, offering nuanced perspectives on their role and significance in contemporary digital culture. By meticulously analyzing the characteristics and functions of weblogs, Herring and her colleagues contribute to a deeper understanding of the ethical implications and communicative practices within online communities, thereby informing educators and practitioners in their efforts to foster responsible and ethical digital engagement among learners.

Michael A. Kaufman [18] embarks on a comprehensive exploration of digital literacy and ethics within educational contexts, delving into the multifaceted dynamics of interaction between educators and students in online learning environments. Kaufman's scholarly inquiries illuminate the evolving conceptual landscape surrounding digital literacy, emphasizing the increasing importance of digital competencies in navigating the complexities of the digital era. Through critical analysis and empirical investigation, Kaufman highlights the intricate relationship between digital literacy, ethical engagement, and educational outcomes, underscoring the imperative for educators to cultivate a holistic understanding of digital literacy and ethics among students. His seminal work serves as a foundational framework for educators seeking to enhance students' digital literacy skills and foster responsible digital citizenship in an increasingly interconnected world.

Castells M., a prominent scholar in the field of media studies, underscores the technomercocratic belief underpinning internet culture, emphasizing its profound impact on human progress and societal development [19].

Collectively, the scholarly endeavors of these researchers contribute to a deeper understanding of digital ethics and behavior within online communities, particularly within educational contexts. Their research not only illuminates the challenges and complexities inherent in digital engagement but also provides valuable insights and strategies for educators and practitioners seeking to navigate the ethical dimensions of digital communication and interaction in educational settings.

Research methods.

The investigation encompassed a cohort of 200 students and 50 educators affiliated with the Kazakh National Pedagogical University, known as the Abai University. Our inquiry into virtual behavioral interactions within the realm of online learning and communication necessitated the application of various research methodologies and techniques: 1. Examination of audio and video recordings from online instructional sessions was employed as a primary means of inquiry. Through meticulous analysis, we scrutinized the behavioral manifestations exhibited by both instructors and learners. Key parameters under scrutiny encompassed the cadence of speech delivery, degrees of affective involvement, levels of learner activity, collaborative pedagogical endeavors, and the frequency of engagement with interactive teaching modalities; 2. Complementing our investigation, we deployed comprehensive questionnaires and surveys tailored to students, designed to assess their perceptions concerning the quality of interaction within online learning environments. Principal dimensions under scrutiny included digital proficiency, the lucidity and efficacy of educational content delivery, levels of learner engagement, and the accessibility of supplementary educational resources; 3. To evaluate the preparedness of educators for facilitating discourse-driven interactions within virtual communities, we conducted targeted interrogations, seeking insights into their attitudes and competencies vis-à-vis online engagement platforms; 4. Leveraging the interactive functionalities inherent in online learning platforms,

such as chat rooms and forums, we engaged in systematic scrutiny of textual exchanges. This endeavor aimed to discern prevalent themes, pinpoint areas of contention or ambiguity, and identify instances warranting additional instructional support; 5. Adopting a multifaceted approach encompassing observation, testing, and interviews, we engaged both teachers and students in our investigative endeavors. Notably, this involved the application of established methodologies such as O. S. Posypanova's "Tendency to Conspicuous Consumption" and M. Rokeach's "Value Orientations" framework. Through the employment of these methodological frameworks, we endeavored to derive nuanced insights into the underlying dynamics governing behaviors and attitudes within the online learning milieu.

Results and discussion. The results of the survey among teachers and students were analyzed and presented in Figure 1. It was expected that the time spent

by students on network communication would constitute the main share in the structure of time distribution. However, students mostly spend time searching for the necessary information for study or work (55%), but communication comes in second place (25%). A fifth of students spend time searching for information related to their hobby. Search videos do not occupy significant positions (5%). Of all the methods of communication, students choose social networks (88%) and message delivery programs (43%). The most popular mobile applications among Kazakh users and students are Instagram, Facebook, Whatsapp, Telegram, and only then VKontakte and Odnoklassniki [20].

The following tasks are solved through social networks: prompt resolution of organizational issues; notifying students; communication with students, including on issues not related to studies - consulting on the academic discipline and accepting assignments (53%); organization of research activities; implementation of student projects based on social networks.

Figure 1. - Preferred method of communication between students and teachers

To test the digital awareness of students, the research sample was divided according to the principle of digital literacy into control and experimental groups. The experimental results obtained for diagnosing the initial level of digital awareness - the ability to be aware

of one's actions and effects in the digital space (questionnaire) are presented in Fig. 2. The results obtained on the initial level of digital awareness among students, obtained as a result of subjective individual assessment, diagnosis and self-diagnosis, indicate the prevalence of low and medium levels.

Figure 2. – Initial level of digital awareness of students.

We also conducted a survey to determine the presence of communicative attitudes among students. These included the following indicators: veiled negativism in judgments about others, justified negativism in judgments, negative personal experience of communicating with teachers and others. Interpreting the experimental results obtained, it should be noted that the test students showed high indicators of signs of a negative communicative attitude; almost 50% of the total score was higher than the general average. But it should be noted that with the increase in digital awareness of both students and teachers, communication attitudes have

become positive. We conducted a survey and subsequent analysis of teachers' readiness for dialogue interaction in online "on-line communities". The interpretation of the results showed that teachers have a positive motivation for interactive participation in network communication; digital literacy and digital competence of teachers is at high and average levels; knowledge of digital etiquette is also at high and medium levels (Table 1).

The outcomes of the survey conducted among both educators and students underwent meticulous

analysis and are delineated in Figure 1. It was anticipated that the bulk of students' time allocation within their schedules would be allocated to online communication endeavors. However, our findings revealed that students predominantly dedicate their time to information retrieval pertinent to their academic or professional pursuits (55%), with communication activities ranking as the second most prevalent activity (25%). A notable portion of students also allocates time to pursuing information aligned with personal interests or hobbies. Video searches, on the other hand, occupy a comparatively minor proportion of their time (5%). Among various communication modalities, students exhibit a pronounced preference for social networking platforms (88%) and messaging applications (43%). Noteworthy mobile applications favored by both Kazakh users and students include Instagram, Facebook, WhatsApp, and Telegram, with VKontakte and Odnoklassniki following suit [20]. Social networks serve multifaceted functions for students, including the expedient resolution of administrative matters, dissemination of timely information, engagement in academic discourse, provision of consultation on academic matters, and facilitation of collaborative research endeavors. Additionally, social networks serve as a platform for executing student projects. To assess students' digital literacy, the research sample was bifurcated into control and experimental groups based on the principle of digital literacy. The experimental findings pertaining to the initial assessment of digital literacy—defined as the ability to comprehend one's actions and their ramifications within the

digital realm—are delineated in Figure 2. Results gleaned from subjective individual assessments, diagnostic evaluations, and self-appraisals reveal a preponderance of students exhibiting low to moderate levels of digital literacy. Furthermore, a survey was conducted to gauge students' communicative predispositions, encompassing indicators such as veiled negativity in interpersonal judgments, justified negativity in assessments, and negative personal experiences in communicative encounters. Interpretation of experimental findings underscores a propensity among test participants toward negative communicative attitudes, with nearly half of the aggregate score exceeding the mean. Nonetheless, a salient observation is the positive correlation observed between heightened levels of digital literacy among both students and educators and the cultivation of more favorable communicative dispositions.

Additionally, an inquiry was conducted, followed by a comprehensive analysis, to ascertain educators' preparedness for engaging in dialogic interactions within online communities. Interpretation of findings unveils a positive inclination among teachers toward active participation in networked communication. Notably, educators demonstrate commendable levels of digital literacy and competence, with a concomitant proficiency in digital etiquette, as evidenced by high and moderate competency levels documented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Performance indicators for network communication interaction		
Levels	Indicators	Diagnostic methods
Motivational	Positive motivation of teachers for network communication interaction « on-line community »	Interview, survey, questionnaire, content analysis of messages on the forum
Informational	Information, digital and media competence of teachers	Conducting seminars and networking forums and analyzing them
Active	Abilities and skills of dialogue communication with students “ on-line” community »	Participant observation, analysis.

The facilitation of dialogue interaction within online communities between students and educators' hinges upon the nuanced consideration of psychological, personal, age-related, and cognitive attributes inherent to the participants. This consideration inherently dictates the structuring of educational processes into distinct organizational frameworks. A salient measure indicative of the efficacy of fostering a culture of networked communication within these online communities lies in the enhancement of educational outcomes.

An analysis of experimental findings utilizing the "Tendency to Conspicuous Consumption" methodology, authored by O. S. Posypanova, revealed discernible associations between demonstrative behavior levels, student activity, and the depth of networked communicative culture. These findings were predicated on gauging the extent of immersion into the virtual realm, with a notable positive correlation ($p = 0.8$) observed between absorption levels and the exhibition of demonstrative behavior. Statistical scrutiny further unveiled correlation dependencies, wherein heightened commu-

nication values, indicative of a subset of social behaviors, were positively correlated with active, robust lifestyles characterized by emotional richness, camaraderie, and public acknowledgment. Concurrently, an inclination towards public visibility was observed to manifest through expressions of respect towards peers, teamwork, and communal appreciation. Such observations underscore the intricate interplay between virtual behavior and the broader social fabric.

Furthermore, the examination of communication values within internet-mediated interactions, as delineated by M. Rokeach's "Value Orientations" methodology, revealed noteworthy trends. Individuals engaging in active virtual communication exhibited a propensity towards prioritizing love (average=2.8; $p < 0.001$) and cultivating deep, enduring friendships (average=6.2; $p < 0.05$) as terminal values. Conversely, users exhibiting medium to low levels of activity predominantly emphasized health, both physical and mental, as their primary terminal value. Instrumental values among active virtual communicators gravitated towards attributes

such as cheerfulness and a penchant for humor (average=4.3; $p < 0.01$), whereas those less engaged leaned towards values of responsibility, duty, and integrity (average = 5.3; $p < 0.05$). These discernments shed light on the nuanced preferences and orientations inherent to students' virtual engagements, reflecting patterns of social behavior underscored by demonstrative conduct, social desirability, communicative values, social endorsement, and public visibility.

Conclusion. In conclusion, a comprehensive socio-psychological examination of the network communicative culture among educators and students has yielded insights into the discernment and interrelation of social and psychological determinants within the online educational milieu. The concept of communicative online culture embodies a multifaceted amalgamation of motivations, cognitive constructs, values, norms, and competencies acknowledged within virtual communities. It encompasses adeptness in leveraging both verbal and non-verbal modalities to facilitate effective interaction. The efficacy of educational stakeholders' engagement within networked environments hinges upon the cultivation of a holistic array of attributes. These include intrinsic motivation and preparedness for online interaction, proficiency in communicative competencies, adeptness in information management, receptivity to innovative practices, and a commitment to professional growth and creativity. Scholarly discourse by domestic researchers underscores the pedagogical efficacy inherent in harnessing social networking platforms. They contend that such platforms serve as conduits for facilitating meaningful interaction between educators and learners, thereby facilitating collaborative endeavors, fostering long-term educational pursuits, facilitating international exchanges, and addressing pivotal educational imperatives. The pervasive immersion of contemporary students within the digital sphere underscores the imperative for a rigorous appraisal of the digital landscape vis-à-vis educational imperatives. Accordingly, there exists a pressing need for institutions of higher learning to proactively tailor educational frameworks to accommodate the evolving dynamics of digital engagement. This entails bespoke strategies for cultivating network communicative culture and the ongoing refinement of innovative pedagogical methodologies geared towards inculcating digital etiquette among educators and students alike.

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